

The above results lead to the conclusion that the silver complex formed will be formulated as $\text{Ag}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S})$.

The complex when analysed gives the following results: C, 29.67% ; H, 1.68% ; N, 15.23% ; Ag, 29.78%. These point to the formula given above for the complex. The proposed formula requires C, 30.08 ; H, 1.94 ; N, 15.59 ; Ag, 30.08%.

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BEHAVIOUR OF CHLORONITROBENZENES WITH HYDRAZINE AND HYDRAZINE DERIVATIVES: HYDRAZOBENZENES

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Interaction between a benzene derivative having a reactive halogen atom, viz., picryl chloride, and phenylhydrazine was employed by Fischer (*Annalen*, 1887, 190, 132) to prepare 2:4:6-trinitrohydrazobenzene. Subsequently, by reacting benzene derivatives having a labile halogen atom with phenylhydrazine and substituted phenylhydrazines, Willgerodt and collaborators (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1661 ; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1882, ii, 37, 351 ; 1891, 43, 490 ; 1891, 44, 72, 452) obtained 2'-chloro-, 3'-chloro- and 4'-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-, -2:4-dinitro-, 3'-chloro-, 4'-chloro- and 4'-bromo-2:4-dinitrohydrazobenzenes. Werner and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3266) prepared 2:4:2'-trinitro-, 2:4:3'-trinitro- and 2:4:4'-trinitrohydrazobenzenes.

Giusa and co-workers (*Gazzetta*, 1918, 48, 8 ; 1921, 51, 307 ; 1922, 52, 346 ; 1923, 53, 165 ; *Atti R. Acad. Lincei*, 1918, v, 27, 379) and Mangini (*Gazzetta*, 1935, 65, 1191) prepared by substitution of a labile nitro group some derivatives of hydrazobenzene, such as, 5-chloro-2:4-dinitro-, 5-bromo-2:4-dinitro-, 5-chloro-2:4'-dinitro-, -4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, -2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 5-chloro-2:4'-dinitro-, 4:6-dinitro-2':3-dimethyl- and 4:6-dinitro-3:4'-dimethylhydrazobenzenes.

During the present investigations some substituted hydrazobenzenes have been prepared by keeping polynitro compounds having a labile halogen atom with phenylhydrazine (1:2) in alcohol at room temperature (15°-20°) for 3 to 4 days. 3-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-4:6-dinitro-, 2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-, 4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 4:6-dinitro-2-methyl-, 2:4:6-trinitro-3-methylhydrazobenzenes have been obtained from 1-chloro-3-bromo-4:6-dinitro-, 1:2-dichloro-4:6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 1-chloro-4:6-dinitro-2-methyl- and 1-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-benzenes and phenylhydrazine in this way.

Attempts to prepare the corresponding hydrazobenzenes from 1:4-dichloro- and 1:4-dibromo-2:6-dinitrobenzenes were not successful. These compounds and phenylhydrazine even in dilute alcoholic solutions afford on keeping for one hour the corresponding 6-halogeno-4-nitro-2-phenylbenzotriazoles. This can be attributed to the ease with which their hydrazobenzenes cyclise.

On the other hand, 6-chloro-1-bromo-2:4-dinitro-3-methyl-, 1:6-dibromo-2:4-dinitro-3-methyl-, 4-chloro-1-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl- and 1:4-dibromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-benzenes and phenylhydrazine do not react at room temperature on keeping for several days. Even when their solutions in absolute alcohol are boiled, the reaction takes place to a small extent, affording only the corresponding 2-phenylbenzotriazoles in poor yields: Hydrazobenzene derivatives could not be isolated in any case.

Hydrazobenzenes.—Alcoholic solutions of the reactive halogen compounds and phenylhydrazine (1:2) were kept at room temperature (15°-20°) for four days. The hydrazobenzenes separated in crystalline forms. These were crystallised from benzene.

Hydrazobenzenes obtained from different reactive halogen compounds together with their characteristics are shown below.

Halogeno-nitrobenzene used.	Hydrazobenzene formed.	% Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1-Chloro-3-bromo-4:6-dinitro-	* 3-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-	56	170°	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl, 11.36	11.50%
1:2-Dichloro-4:6-dinitro-	2-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-	58	168°	Fawn	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl, 11.43	11.50
1-Chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-	2-Bromo-4:6-dinitro-	60	169°	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₄ N ₄ Br	Br, 22.51	22.66
1-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-	*4:6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	50	157°	Do	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄	N, 19.68	19.44
1-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-2-methyl-	4:6-Dinitro-2-methyl-	54	154°	Orange-yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄	N, 19.14	19.44
1-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-	2:4:6-Trinitro-3-methyl-	55°	149°	Orange	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₅	N, 20.73	21.02

* Prepared before by other methods.

The hydrazobenzenes are yellow to orange in colour and are easily soluble in common organic solvents in cold. They readily cyclise; on boiling in alcohol they yield 2-phenylbenzotriazole derivatives, while in acetic acid they form 2-phenylbenzotriazole-1-oxides.